

Doubling housing production in the Paris region: A multi-policy, multi-jurisdictional response

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Abstract

How can metropolitan regions ramp up housing production to meet the demands of a growing population, after years of inadequate construction and mounting challenges for affordability? I consider recent policy reforms in the Paris region that have successfully doubled that area's housing-unit completion rate. I show that a focus on social housing, harnessing of publicly owned land, new financial and regulatory incentives, and the enforcement of municipal policy by higher-level governments have effectively encouraged development. These policies complemented one another and were implemented by multiple levels of government as part of a shared metropolitan strategy. Paris' example offers a model for other regions looking to identify appropriate policies to spur construction.

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Introduction

In the face of rising home prices and apartment rents, housing affordability has become a locus of concern globally (Wetzstein 2017). Stagnant incomes, the financialization of housing, the elimination of rent controls, a desire for more space, and growing inequality have each contributed to the problem (Fields and Hodkinson 2018). So has inadequate housing production, which adds pressure on a constrained market. Dense and more populous communities where construction is made difficult because of regulatory, geographical, financial, or other barriers face particular challenges in providing homes for low- and moderate-income families (Kallergis et al. 2018; Saks 2008). What policies can urban regions pursue to induce more building?

In this paper, I argue that the combination of a broad array of disparate policies promoted by multiple levels of government enabled the Paris metropolitan region to roughly double unit construction over a short period beginning in 2015. This increase in construction cannot be explained by national or global economic conditions, but rather must be understood as the result of a government-led attack on the housing-production problem. I characterize the policies the region pursued as on-the-ground implementation of four approaches often emphasized by scholars and advocates: Producing additional permanently affordable units; exploiting public land; developing financial and regulatory incentives; and requiring municipal planning to meet metropolitan goals.

The first approach—providing additional permanently affordable units—counters declining per-capita government support for subsidized units, a trend in countries such as the U.K. and U.S. (Scalon et al. 2014; Vale and Freemark 2019), and addresses lower-income-family needs. In Germany, for example, home prices have risen significantly more quickly than incomes since the mid-1990s (Dahl and Góralczyk 2017). Investment in public or social housing expands unit availability for rent-burdened families and those threatened by gentrification-induced displacement. But such projects often lack zoning allowances to advance in communities that permit only single-family homes. Moreover, in the face of a persistent ideological attachment to neoliberal urbanization throughout the West—including

housing privatization and welfare-state retrenchment—building support for additional public investment may be difficult (Fields and Hodkinson 2018).

The second approach allocates additional public property for housing, in response to the fact that land is a primary contributor to housing prices. Reduced-cost public land lessens project investment expenditures. California’s Governor Gavin Newsom, following in this vein, has proposed allocating state land for housing construction (Dillon 2019). Yet its use for housing also means less room for other local priorities, such as commercial space, and fewer potential revenues for cash-starved governments.

The third approach suggests that regulatory burdens are a primary contributor to housing costs (Quigley and Raphael 2005), and thus that new rules or incentives are necessary for production. Building is made pricier because of, for example, design standards or minimum-lot-size requirements, but altering such regulations threatens industries reliant on current codes. Moreover, many low-income neighborhoods cannot induce construction because of difficulties attracting a market of potential renters and buyers—so subsidies, which may be difficult to generate given limited governmental expenditures, may be necessary to complete certain investments.

Finally, the fourth approach recommends higher-level governments mandate rules that allow more development (Freemark 2019), given that local exercise of land-use powers often produces low-density zoning that excludes low-income residents from certain neighborhoods (Schleicher and Hills 2019). U.S. efforts of this sort, however, have been largely reactive in their reliance on developers and have done little to enforce change on unwilling municipalities; they thus have had limited success. Massachusetts’ Section 40B enabled developers to build affordable housing in cities with a deficiency, but has produced only about 35,000 low- and moderate-income units since the 1970s (Infranca 2019), even as the total number of housing units in the state increased by 1,000,000. Similarly, California’s Housing Element requirements, which mandate that local planning match growth, have been oft-ignored by municipalities (Monkkonen et al. 2019).

There are thus reasonable arguments for engaging each of these approaches, but also clear obstacles to their implementation, and few related policies have been more than haphazardly put into place. Nationwide, U.S. per-capita housing production declined by almost 60 percent between the 1960s and 2010s.¹ In the U.K., homebuilding has declined by 40 percent since the 1970s; in the Netherlands, production fell by about 30 percent since 2000, and in Germany, construction is now roughly half 1990s levels (BPD 2016; Wilson and Barton 2018). What would occur in a region's housing market if efforts were undertaken simultaneously on each of the aforementioned fronts? This paper's case study provides some insight. Over the past decade, political actors in the French capital region implemented a coordinated set of policies to encourage housing production. These changes count on additional housing to increase supply, absorbing demand from a growing population and relieving pressure on the market. Paris shows how a region can increase construction over a constrained period by amalgamating a wide variety of related policies, each of which would stand to be further considered in other countries.

I review data and reports produced by French national, regional, and local actors to explore policies they advanced since 2010. I supplement these with insight garnered from interviews with public officials.² I first contextualize what spurred the region into action. Second, I identify and discuss key elements of the region's recent policies. Finally, I consider what lessons the Paris example offers to other regions, while noting which roadblocks may limit long-term policy continuity.

¹ 16.9 million privately owned housing units were started in the average year in the 1960s, compared to 11.7 million on average per year from 2010 to 2018; the U.S. population was 181 million in 1960 versus 309 million in 2010. See U.S. Census Bureau and U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development, *Housing Starts: Total: New Privately Owned Housing Units Started, 1959-2019*.

² I conducted interviews as part of a related study from January–March 2019 with 41 stakeholders, including 16 elected officials (mayors, councilors, and regional representatives), and 25 government staff. Interviews lasted 1.5 hours on average.

Decades of inertia and rising housing costs

Politically, Paris' urban area generally corresponds with Île-de-France, a dense region with more than 12 million inhabitants. Île-de-France is divided into eight départements (counties) and more than 1,200 municipalities. The city/county of Paris itself accounts for less than 20 percent of the regional population and less than one percent of its land area.

The region's built environment and demographics changed considerably in the 30 years of economic and population growth following WWII. During this period, the national government managed land-use investment, using public development corporations to concentrate hundreds of thousands of housing units on exurban sites, often in new towns (Lelévrier and Melic 2018). Many units were explicitly affordable (60 percent of today's social housing was completed before 1975), often in 'grand ensemble' concrete towers (Arènes and Richon 2018).

Yet public officials halted this construction program as economic growth slowed in the mid-1970s and as social-housing complexes isolated from jobs and services became ghettoized (Lelévrier and Melic 2018). The central government pursued several reforms. It shifted subsidies away from social housing and toward homeownership (Wijburg 2019). And it decentralized decision-making, giving regional governments like Île-de-France power to create plans, while shifting land-use control to localities (Pinson and Le Galès 2005). Mayors, Prost (2015: 24) notes, were 'praised as the real representatives of local democracy, bec[oming] a central element of political life.'

The national-government pullout subjected construction to the whims of local officials, 'whose inclination to densify land use is limited' (Driant 2012), and housing production flagged. Whereas in the 1980s, about 47,000 units were produced annually in Île-de-France, this figure declined to about 37,000 in the 2000s (the region's population increased by 20 percent over this period). Population-adjusted construction declined to half the rate of several other French regions (Driant 2012); Île-de-France's share of national production tumbled from 17.8 percent to 12.1 percent from 1990 to 2011 (Cour des

comptes 2015). Paris' city planners in 2011 were morose, arguing that construction 'can only fall further in the coming years' (APUR 2011: 9).

Regional living costs increased dramatically over the past few decades (Freemark and Steil 2019), and because of the slow ramp-up in social-housing units, mobility is low, making it difficult for young households to find reasonable-cost apartments (Cour des comptes 2015). This occurred despite repeated plans to address the housing crisis from the 1970s through 2000s (Sabbah 2016). The 1994 regional plan (SDRIF), for example, proposed 53,000 new housing units annually (Cour des comptes 2015). But far fewer were completed.

Limited production resulted, at least partly, from a missing 'sentiment of being part of a shared, metropolitan destiny,' according to Le Hervet (2012: 3). But the perception of local isolation shifted in the early 2000s. Upon entering office in 2001, Paris Mayor Bertrand Delanoë concentrated city attention to metropolitan-scale cooperative planning (Driant and Lévy-Vroelant 2019). French President Nicholas Sarkozy, elected in 2007, reemphasized the national government's role, promoting a vision for a 'Grand Paris' focused on reinforcing the region's competitiveness through a new metro system, business hubs, and a surge in housing production (Préfet d'Île-de-France 2018c). Below, I show how these approaches catalyzed a doubling in construction.

Policies for Île-de-France housing production

Following Sarkozy's lead, the National Assembly passed 2010 legislation targeting constructing 70,000 units annually in Île-de-France to accommodate the housing deficit for existing residents and the needs of a growing population (Poncelet et al. 2018). The Île-de-France government, tasked with developing the regional plan, approved a 2013 SDRIF reaffirming this objective, while preserving a greenbelt to limit greenfield projects and champion transit-adjacent, dense infill.³ With construction as its primary

³ Sarkozy's government, which had oversight, prevented the region from passing a SDRIF in 2008 (it originally had a 60,000-unit annual goal) because he wanted it to incorporate his Grand Paris proposals. The right-wing national government

goal, the SDRIF noted ‘housing, foundational for equity... but also economic attractiveness, requires massive and quality production, particularly for social housing’ (Île-de-France 2013: 7). Legally, the SDRIF is substantiated through local land-use plans, which must be altered to comply within three years of SDRIF passage.

The SDRIF and the Grand Paris law set the table for implementation, launching a cascade of new, multi-governmental policies, particularly in 2014 and 2015. One explanation for their quick execution, according to interviewees, was consensus about the need to do *something* about the region’s housing challenges. Interviewees emphasized that Sarkozy’s Grand Paris idea encouraged them to espouse a shared metropolitan agenda. As such there has thus far been little opposition, even with changes in partisan control among governments concerned.⁴ In this section, I organize policies within a series of four themes, summarized in Table 1, which identifies government levels involved.

[Table 1 about here]

A. Focus on affordable housing

Social housing—defined here as government-subsidized, project-based affordable housing⁵—has been a key French policy since the 19th century. As noted, decentralization reduced the volume of social-housing construction, though by 2018, Île-de-France had 1.26 million social units (Pagès 2018). These were funded through government subsidies, a reduced value-added tax (VAT) for construction,

and the left-wing regional government spent much of the period between 2009 and 2013 fighting over appropriate routes for the new metro lines and their purpose.

⁴ Control over the national government shifted from right to left (2012), then to the center (2017). The regional government shifted from left to right (2014). Many cities saw changes in partisan control after the 2014 elections.

⁵ French social housing is accessible to a range of family incomes equivalent to about two-thirds of the population, not just the poorest (Scanlon et al. (2014: 335) argue that social-housing allocation in Europe ranges from universalistic, such as in Denmark and Sweden, to generalist, such as in Austria and France, to targeted, such as in the U.K. and Ireland, where public units are reserved for the least well-off; the U.S. would fall in the latter category as well). Separate subsidy categories address very-low-income (PLAI); low-income (PLUS); and moderate income (PLS) families; an additional category (PLI) is designed for middle-income families—though these units do not count for municipal achievement of SRU goals. Social housing can be constructed by non-profit providers, local authorities, and public developers. Recent Île-de-France social-housing has been 15% PLAI; 55% PLUS; 25% PLS and 5% PLI (Pagès et al. 2018).

allowances for property-tax exoneration, local-government guarantees, and low-interest loans from the Caisse des Dépôts (CDC), the national public investment bank (APUR 2011).

The SDRIF prioritized social housing, arguing that more units were needed to ‘enable households to move’ (Île-de-France 2013: 87). It proposed that regional housing stock be 30 percent social by 2030, from 23.5 percent in 2015 (Poncelet et al. 2018). Similarly, the national government’s 2000 SRU legislation, and a 2013 amendment, required communities to make space for affordable units in the context of unequal distribution between municipalities. Every Île-de-France city with more than 1,500 inhabitants—even the wealthiest—must achieve 25 percent social housing by 2025 (Cour des comptes 2015).⁶

These policies had a real impact. First, a large share (31 percent) of all units built between 2011 and 2017 were social (Poncelet et al. 2018). Second, more were built; in 2017, 30,183 social-housing units were completed, compared to 13,219 in 2003—the contemporary nadir (Préfet d’Île-de-France 2018c). Third, cities concerned by the SRU increased social-housing shares from 13.2 to 15.9 percent on average between 2002 and 2011 (Cour des comptes 2015). The city of Paris, fulfilling the ambitions of socialist councils, took the goal particularly seriously, funding 100,000 units from 2001 to 2019 and increasing the permanently affordable share of units from 13.4 to an estimated 22.2 percent between 2001 and 2020 (Paris 2019). This broad increase in social-housing construction contrasts dramatically with global trends of privatization and reduced social support (Fields and Hodkinson 2018).

Interviewees noted that municipal housing production advanced as a whole due to SRU mandates. Cities that valued housing for higher-income families produced more units overall because they were required to incorporate social housing into new developments, and land and funding were

⁶ There is significant variation between communities in terms of their current social-housing levels. Whereas many communities northeast of the city of Paris have more than 40% of their housing in the social sector, many wealthy communities to the west have fewer than 20% social (Arènes and Richon 2018). These divergences have begun to converge as a result of the SRU law (Freemark and Steil 2019).

available (see below). The completion of social-housing units thus constitutes a major element of the region's overall production increase.

B. Harnessing public land

Governments pursued several policies to leverage public property for construction. Sarkozy prioritized station-area construction; in initial proposals, the national-government metro constructor—Société du Grand Paris (SGP)—would hold eminent-domain redevelopment power. This vision, however, emphasized economic development rather than housing affordability (Enright 2016); moreover, legislators ultimately required SGP to make redevelopment agreements with affected municipalities. Even so, SGP has advanced several station-area joint developments, and metro construction has encouraged cities to re-plan locally owned land near stops. Interviewees emphasized that the metro catalyzed many large developments.

Other policies linked public land with housing construction. First, national government-controlled developers and local-government developers—which together account for a fifth of regional production—intensified investment. Following a 2014 directive from the regional prefect (the national government's representative), national developers tripled building between 2010–2013 and 2014–2017 (Préfet d'Île-de-France 2018b). In 2017 alone, these developers began 18,000 housing units, from 9,500 in 2015 (Paruta 2018). Several interviewees noted that their municipal development companies also ramped up planning and site identification because of the housing goal.

Second, a 2014 national housing law encouraged mobilizing land (by all levels of government) for housing (Cour des comptes 2015). In 2015, the national government identified 70 publicly owned sites for 7,900 housing units, of which 45 percent would be social (Commission nationale de l'aménagement, de l'urbanisme et du foncier 2016). Public enterprises promoted production. For example, the SNCF railway agreed to complete 8,000 housing units across seven sites in Paris previously devoted to infrastructure (Le Moniteur 2016). Working through an intermediary, the regional

government increased land transfers for housing by 50 percent between 2013 and 2018 (EPF Île-de-France 2019).

C. Financial and regulatory incentives

France is relatively welcoming to new construction; compared to neighboring Germany and the Netherlands, the country had more than 50 percent higher per-capita construction levels between 2000 and 2015 (BPD 2016). Interviewees emphasized the present ease of attracting private-developer investment, due to high housing demand. A number of financial incentives developed by local, regional, and national governments support that investment by reinforcing assistance for first-time homebuyers, while expanding the rental market. But these approaches in themselves do not explain the boost in construction that occurred in Île-de-France after 2015, since they were preexisting.

Several new policies tackling the cost of construction and the regulatory impediments to building supported Paris-region development. First, the government promoted ‘intermediary’ housing, designed for families with incomes too low to afford market-rate units, but too high to qualify for traditional social housing.⁷ A 2014 national law provided such units in dense, transit-accessible areas a lower purchasing VAT, allowances for property-tax exoneration, and the ability to incorporate units into social-housing projects. Regional intermediary housing production increased from 3,000 to 5,000 units between 2015 and 2018 (Joinet and Pauquet 2019).

Second, new policies at multiple levels filled in the financial gap. The regional government increased direct housing grants. The national government supported social-housing construction, signing a pact with the CDC and Action Logement (which collects certain employment taxes) to finance 30,000 social-housing units (Escudié 2014).⁸ It provided reduced land purchase price and reduced construction

⁷ One-bedroom social-housing units, for example, rent at around 8€ per square meter, versus 18.4€ per square meter for market rate (Joinet and Pauquet 2019).

⁸ The CDC’s low-cost loans (typically 40-50 years long) are financed by several banking products, such as the Livret A, offered in commercial banks, and which CDC centralizes. Loan rates are adjusted based on the level of affordability of the

VAT for social-housing projects (Commission nationale de l'aménagement, de l'urbanisme et du foncier 2016). And interviewees noted that local governments increasingly reduce property-tax burdens for any new housing.

Finally, several regulatory changes reduced costs by making projects more feasible. Alterations in the national building code in 2014 and 2015 reduced expensive accessibility requirements (République Française 2015). And a 2014 national law eliminated floor-area-ratio limits in local plans. Though cities retained power over building heights and ground coverage, this made small-scale, infill projects more feasible throughout the country.⁹

D. Enforcement from above

Regional and national housing objectives could have been undermined by city councils that historically have been more concerned about maintaining the status quo than construction. Yet national and regional governments developed enforcement policies to spread the burden. This effort took several forms. First, the national government deployed data systems to identify where housing was built (Préfet d'Île-de-France 2015). Second, it instructed the prefect in 2013 to rigorously impose SRU requirements through budgetary fines on municipalities not on track to achieve their 25 percent social-housing goal (Actu.fr 2018). The prefect's power includes the ability to use eminent domain to seize land in non-conforming municipalities; it can then transfer land to developers (République Française 2014). According to interviewees, this threat encouraged cities to accelerate social-housing projects.

Third, national and regional plans were enforced. The Grand Paris law allowed the prefect to identify housing-production goals for sub-territories throughout the region, subdividing the SDRIF-defined levels (Cour des comptes 2015). Relatedly, the prefect reviews (and can force modifications of)

social-housing units. It is worth noting that inhabitants can take advantage of (entitlement) housing vouchers to help pay the cost of rents.

⁹ Depending on the circumstance, this rule change (in the ALUR law) could significantly increase allowed building sizes. See Dominique Lorrain (2018), *L'urbanisme 1.0*, Paris: Raisons d'Agir.

local zoning to ensure conformance with housing-growth objectives. The national government, meanwhile, attempted to curb parochialism encouraged by local planning practices; 2014 and 2015 laws transferred zoning and public housing authorities to new sub-regional entities (Arènes and Richon 2018; Préfet d'Île-de-France 2018a).¹⁰

Results: Sharp production increase

These policy changes had a cumulatively dramatic effect. Between 1991 and 2014, annual production in Île-de-France averaged 43,000 units, and never surpassed 51,000 units. This figure expanded mightily; in 2017 and 2018, housing authorized increased to 98,300 and 89,200 units, respectively (Osouf and Monier 2019). About 80,000 units, roughly a third social, entered into construction in both years. These units were spread across both wealthy areas and poorer ones (Préfet d'Île-de-France 2018c). Figure 1 documents the increase in construction occurring after 2015, demonstrating the impact of the new policies.

[Figure 1 about here]

The increase focused on infill. While only 14 percent of units completed from 1975 to 2006 were in the near-suburbs, that figure increased to half in recent years (Poncelet et al. 2018). As of 2019, annual production expanded by 110 percent in inner suburbs, compared to the period from 2005 to 2014, versus by 71 percent in outer suburbs (Osouf and Monier 2019). The effort to spur construction was thus not primarily predicated on the bulldozing of natural and agricultural land.

Contextually, these figures are impressive. Île-de-France's share of national housing production expanded from 10 percent in 2006 to 20 percent in 2017 (Osouf and Monier 2019); the increase therefore cannot be ascribed to widespread changes in France. Similarly, there is no evidence to link the trend with commonalities among global cities; in 2017, for example, New York City permitted only

¹⁰ Some interviewees were skeptical of those new entities' effectiveness, arguing that cities retained informal control over most local planning. The impact of these entities is thus not yet clear.

about 20,000 units, and London started only 19,000 (New York City Department of City Planning 2018; U.K. Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government 2019)—both about a third of the per-capita Paris-region rate. Finally, changes did not reflect a generalized come-back from the Great Recession; national construction in France was lower in 2015 than in 2009 (Haran and Kaldi 2017), and Figure 1 shows Île-de-France production was not largely impacted by that slowdown. The increase can thus reasonably be understood as a response to policy changes, not to broader economic conditions.

Conclusion

Paris-region officials achieved their goal of doubling housing production, despite pessimism less than 10 years ago that such an expansion was feasible. Île-de-France suggests that limited construction in countries throughout the West is hardly an immutable condition. I have discussed how a focus on social housing, harnessing of public land, financial and regulatory incentives, and enforcement of local plans from above have spurred production. This combination required political leadership at multiple governmental levels, and has been far more effective than previous, halting efforts.

The policies complemented one another in a way that previous efforts pursued individually did not. Public land availability, for example, made space for social housing. Prefect enforcement of SRU and SDRIF goals required localities to open space for construction, which was made more feasible thanks to additional funding. More research, however, must identify the impact of these changes in terms of affordability—especially as compared to policies aimed at issues unrelated to construction. Additional evidence is necessary to quantify each policy’s individual impact.

The longevity of these policies, moreover, is unknown. Recent elections of anti-development officials in some municipalities suggests finite consensus about housing needs (Sabbah 2016). Moreover, social-housing production slowed somewhat in 2018 because of difficulties putting projects in the ground, and national-government support is tenuous. Nevertheless, the Paris-region example

suggests a path forward. For countries looking for effective approaches to get more units in the ground, the policies pursued in France could be a good place to start.

References

Note: Acronyms used in references are APUR for Atelier parisien d'urbanisme and DRIEA for Direction régionale et interdépartementale de l'Équipement et de l'Aménagement d'Île-de-France. Quotes in the text were translated by the author.

Actu.fr (2018). Logements sociaux. Un effort de construction accru, mais les pénalités aussi. February 20.

APUR (2011). “Quelle production de logements en Ile-de-France dans le contexte économique actuel ?” October.

Jean-François Arènes and Jeanne Richon (2018). “Les Chiffres du Logement Social de la Métropole du Grand Paris.” Paris: APUR.

BPD (2016). Germany, France, The Netherlands. Housing markets in perspective.

Commission nationale de l'aménagement, de l'urbanisme et du foncier (2016). Rapport sur la mise en œuvre du dispositif de mobilisation du foncier public en faveur du logement. February.

Cour des comptes (2015). “Le logement en Île-de-France: Donner de la Cohérence à l'Action Publique.” Paris.

Juliana Dahl and Małgorzata Góralczyk (2017). Recent Supply and Demand Developments in the German Housing Market. European Commission.

Liam Dillon (2019). “Gov. Gavin Newsom threatens to cut state funding from cities that don't approve enough housing.” *Los Angeles Times*. January 10.

Jean-Claude Driant (2012). “Why isn't there enough housing in France?” Translated by Oliver Waine. *Metropolitics*.

Jean-Claude Driant and Claire Lévy-Vroelant (2019). “In search of equity.” In Rainer Wehrhahn, Jörg Pohlen, Christine Hannemann, Frank Othengrafen, and Brigitta Schmidt-Lauber (eds.), *Housing and Housing Politics in European Metropolises*. Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-22345-8_2

Theresa Enright (2016). *The Making of Grand Paris*. Cambridge: MIT Press. DOI: 10.7551/mitpress/10476.001.0001

EPF Île-de-France (2019). Renforcement et diversification de la mobilisation foncière en Île-de-France.

Jean-Noël Escudié (2014). “Logement – Ile-de-France : un pacte regional pour produire plus de 30.000 logements sociaux par an.” Paris: Banque des Territoires.

Desiree J. Fields and Stuart N. Hodkinson (2018). “Housing Policy in Crisis: An International Perspective.” *Housing Policy Debate* 28(1): 1-5. DOI: 10.1080/10511482.2018.1395988

Yonah Freemark (2019). “Upzoning Chicago: Impacts of a Zoning Reform on Property Values and Housing Construction.” *Urban Affairs Review*. In press. DOI: 10.1177/1078087418824672

Yonah Freemark and Justin Steil (2019). “Affordable housing caught in the crosshairs of regional fragmentation” Working paper.

Île-de-France (2013). Schéma Directeur de la Région Île-de-France.

Louise Haran and Matthias Kaldi (2017). Le parc des logements. Paris: Observatoire des logements.

John Infranca (2019). “The New State Zoning.” *Boston College Law Review* 60. 823.

Hélène Joinet and Philippe Pauquet (2019). Note rapide : Le logement locatif intermédiaire s’installe dans le paysage francilien. Paris: Institut d’Aménagement et d’Urbanisme d’Île-de-France.

Achilles Kallergis, Shlomo Angel, Yang Liu, Alejandro M. Blei, Nicolás Galarza Sanchez, and Patrick Lamson-Hall (2018). Housing Affordability in a Global Perspective. Working Paper. Lincoln Institute of Land Policy.

Maud Le Hervet (2012). “Le logement en Île-de-France : une politique fragmentée.” *Métropolitiques*.

Le Moniteur (2016). “La SNCF et la Ville de Paris signent un protocole foncier pour la construction de 8000 logements.” November 29.

Christine Lelévrier and Talia Melic (2018). “Impoverishment and Social Fragmentation in Housing Estates of the Paris Region, France.” In Daniel Baldwin Hess, Tiit Tammaru, and Maarten van Ham (eds.), *Housing Estates in Europe*. Cham: Springer. 313-338. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-92813-5_14

Paavo Monkkonen, Michael Manville, and Spike Friedman (2019). “A Flawed Law.” UCLA Lewis Center for Regional Policy Studies.

New York City Department of City Planning (2018). NYC Housing Production Snapshot.

Nicolas Osouf and Philippe Monier (2019). “La construction de logements en Île-de-France.” Paris: DRIEA.

Emmanuelle Pagès, Alice Genty, Paul Blanchard, Philippe Monier, and Manon Risoul (2018). Le parc locatif social en Île-de-France au 1^{er} janvier 2017. Paris: DRIEA.

Paris (City) (2019). Grand format : Le logement social à Paris. [<https://www.paris.fr/grandsformats/le-logement-social-a-paris-26>]

Stéphanie Paruta (2018). “L’action des aménageurs publics pour la production de logements en Île-de-France.” Paris: DRIEA.

Gilles Pinson and Patrick Le Galès (2005). “State restructuring and decentralization dynamics in France.” Working paper. RTN Urbeurope.

Thomas Poncelet, Phillippe Louchart, Sandra Roger, Éric Chometon, Anne-Laure Wittmann, Benoît Chantoiseau, and Henry Ciesielski (2018). “Évolutions Conjointes du Parc de Logements et de la Population en Île-de-France.” Paris: APUR.

- Préfet d'Île-de-France (2015). "Plan de mobilisation pour le logement en Île-de-France." February 25.
- Préfet d'Île-de-France (2018a). "Les PLU en Île-de-France." Paris: DRIEA.
- Préfet d'Île-de-France (2018b). "Contribution des aménageurs de l'État à la production de logements en Île-de-France." Paris: DRIEA.
- Préfet d'Île-de-France (2018c). "Le Grand Paris du logement." Paris: DRIEA.
- Yannick Prost (2015). "La Métropole du Grand Paris face au défi du logement." *Après-demain* 33. 23-24.
- John Quigley and Steven Raphael (2005). "Regulation and the High Cost of Housing in California." *American Economic Review* 95(2): 323-328. DOI: 10.1257/000282805774670293
- République Française (2014). "Moderniser et sécuriser le droit de préemption exercé par le préfet en communes carencées." Paris: Ministère du Logement, de l'Égalité des Territoires et de la Ruralité.
- République Française (2015). 50 premières mesures de simplification pour la construction de logements. Paris: Ministère du Logement, de L'Égalité des Territoires et de la Ruralité.
- Catherine Sabbah (2016). Logement : l'inefficacité d'une politique unique. *Les Echos*. January 13.
- Raven Saks (2008). "Job creation and housing construction." *Journal of Urban Economics* 64(1): 178-195. DOI: 10.1016/j.jue.2007.12.003
- Kathleen Scalon, Christine Whitehead, and Melissa Fernández Arrigoitia (eds.) (2014). *Social Housing in Europe*. Oxford: John Wiley & Sons. DOI: 10.1002/9781118412367
- David Schleicher and Roderick Hills (2019). "A Not-So-Quiet Revolution in Land-Use Law?" *NYU Furman: The Dream Revisited*. New York.
- Steffen Wetzstein (2017). "The global urban housing affordability crisis." *Urban Studies* 54(14): 3159-3177. DOI: 10.1177/0042098017711649
- Gertjan Wijburg (2019). "Privatised Keynesianism and the state-enhanced diversification of credit." *International Journal of Housing Policy* 19(2): 143-164. DOI: 10.1080/19491247.2017.1397926
- Wendy Wilson and Cassie Barton (2018). Tacking the under-supply of housing in England. United Kingdom House of Commons Library.
- Lawrence Vale and Yonah Freemark (2019). "The Privatization of American Public Housing: Leaving the Poorest of the Poor Behind." In Katrin Anacker, Mai Nguyen, and David Varady (eds.), *The Routledge Handbook of Housing Policy and Planning*. Abingdon: Routledge. 189-206. DOI: 10.4324/9781315642338-15
- U.K. Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government (2019). Table 253: permanent dwellings started and completed, by tenure and district. [<https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/live-tables-on-house-building>]

Table 1: Overview of key housing-production policies

	A. Affordable housing	B. Public land	C. Financial and regulatory incentives	D. Enforcement from above
French national government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SRU law requires 25% social housing per city by 2025 (2000; updated 2013). - Maintenance of pre-existing subsidies for low-income households. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grand Paris metro project incorporates joint-development potential (2010—). - National government and state-owned enterprises encouraged to sell land (2013—). - National developers encouraged to ramp-up production (2014—). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incentives for social and intermediary housing options through reduced tax rates (2014). - Work with national bank to fund new units (2014). - Reduce building code requirements (2014, 2015). - Eliminate floor-area maximums (2014). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National government representative uses fines and threatens eminent domain to enforce SRU (2013—).
Île-de-France regional government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SDRIF regional plan aims for 30% social housing by 2030 (2013). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional government increases land transfers for housing (2014—). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional regional funding for projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enforcement of SDRIF on local plans, requiring minimum construction levels (2013—).
Local governments (e.g., Paris)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desire for new housing in general encourages social housing through mixed-income projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local developers encouraged to ramp-up production (2014—). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governments reduce property taxes for new construction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local planning and housing oversight gradually shifted to higher-level organizations (2014, 2015).

Figure 1: Housing put into construction in Île-de-France region over previous year, 1985–2019

Note: Chart by the author. Information significantly improved beginning in 2016, with quarterly, rather than annual, data. Data from Préfet d'Île-de-France (2019), "Sit@del 2 : Statistiques de la construction neuve en Île-de-France," August 12. [<http://www.driea.ile-de-france.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/sit-del-2-base-de-donnees-sur-la-construction-r202.html>]